

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 5 (2025)

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EFFECTS OF SMOKING, VAPING AND SNIFFING ON THE NERVOUS SYSTEM

Basit Kamran¹, Seema Javeed², Rubama Javed³, Luqman Yousaf⁴, Muhammad Hanzla⁵, Ammar Mehmood⁶

Article Details

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Smoking, Vaping, Nervous System, Comparative Effects, Cognitive Impairment, Anxiety

Basit Kamran

Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Superior University, Lahore

Seema Javeed

Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Superior University, Lahore

Rubama Javed

Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Superior University, Lahore

Luqman Yousaf

Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Superior University, Lahore

Muhammad Hanzla

Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Superior University, Lahore

Ammar Mehmood

Department of Emerging Allied Health Technologies, Superior University, Lahore

Background: In today's era, where trends and patterns of use of various intoxicants are changing, understanding the profound harm they cause to mental, psychological, and physical health is of paramount importance. There is a general perception that vaping or other modern methods are less harmful than traditional smoking.

Methods: A detailed questionnaire was conducted among the individuals with these habits, to record their personal experiences. The key points included in the study included direct identification by the users of neurological and psychological problems such as decreased concentration, memory impairment, persistent headaches, sleep disturbances, excessive anxiety, and mood swings. The data was analyzed by using SPSS. **Results:** This study clearly demonstrates that smoking, vaping, and inhaling habits profoundly affect the human nervous system, leading to significant declines in cognitive and psychological performance. The data showed that users of these three methods reported significantly higher rates of neurological problems such as difficulty concentrating, memory loss, persistent headaches, sleep disturbances, and anxiety. These findings inform all relevant stakeholders about the real risks of these habits in order to promote a healthy lifestyle. **Conclusion:** The final conclusion of this study is that the habits of traditional smoking, vaping, and sniffing various substances have devastating and clearly negative cognitive and psychological effects on the human nervous system. Our results highlighted similar high rates of problems such as memory impairment, lack of concentration, and anxiety among users of all three methods.

INTRODUCTION:

The human nervous system is a very complex and sensitive system that regulates all the functions of the body. This system consists of the brain, spinal cord, and nerves, which are responsible for transmitting messages between different organs. The proper functioning of the nervous system is linked to every aspect of human life, be it movements, sensations, emotions, or the process of thinking and understanding. Even a minor malfunction in this system can have a profound impact on human health and lifestyle (1). The past few decades have seen a rapid increase in smoking and other related habits such as vaping and sniffing. These habits are often considered by the young generation as a means of escape from modern lifestyle or mental stress. However, several scientific studies have shown that all these habits are not only very harmful to physical but also to nervous health (2).

When this system is affected by external chemicals or toxins, the performance of nerve cells is affected. Nicotine, carbon monoxide, and other harmful components in tobacco enter the bloodstream and reach brain cells, disrupting their normal signals (3). Vaping, which is apparently considered a safe alternative to smoking, has actually been shown to be just as harmful. When inhaled, the nicotine, flavoring agents, and metal particles in e-cigarettes increase oxidative stress in brain neurons, which in turn affects memory, attention, and learning ability (4). Similarly, in the process of “sniffing” drugs, the chemicals enter the bloodstream directly through the nasal mucosa and immediately reach the brain, where they disrupt the balance of neurotransmitters. This process can lead to nervous system disorders, anxiety, depression, and even brain damage in the long term (5).

A section of the population is increasingly getting involved in these habits, the main reasons for which include the influence of social media, peer pressure, and an attempt to get temporary relief from mental stress. There is an urgent need for such studies in the field of paramedical science so that health workers can play an effective role in spreading awareness about this. Since the nervous system is the control centre of the human body, the harmful effects on it affect the functions of the entire body (6). Cigarette smoking involves burning tobacco, which gives off a mixture of harmful substances including nicotine, tar, carbon monoxide, and several cancer-causing chemicals that enter the lungs and affect different parts of the body (7). Researchers have long studied how smoking harms the nervous system, showing that it not only causes physical dependence but also contributes to a number of neurological disorders (8).

After inhalation, nicotine quickly passes into the blood and reaches the brain within a few seconds. There, it attaches to nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nAChRs) and triggers the release of dopamine, a chemical that strengthens the desire to continue smoking. Prolonged and chronic smoking has been shown to cause notable neurological and cognitive impairments. For example, studies indicate that the prevalence of smoking among individuals with schizophrenia is significantly higher than in the general population (9).

This study is an attempt to dispel this misconception and to compare the effects of the three behaviours on the nervous system. The results of this study will not only increase public awareness but also enable health experts, educators, and policymakers to take effective measures to prevent these behaviours in the younger generation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This research was quantitative and comparative in nature, aiming to compare the effects of smoking, vaping and sniffing on the human nervous system. This study examined the changes in the nervous system, mental stress, and effects on brain cells after using nicotine through these three methods. The aim of the research was to understand whether vaping and sniffing were really less harmful than smoking, and to what extent these habits affect human mental health. The research was conducted in various educational institutions and medical centers where young people and adults smoke, vape or sniff. The data collected in this study were first cleaned and organized for analysis, after which the Shapiro-Wilk test (Sapphire normality test) was used to assess the distribution of the data. Since the data did not meet the conditions of normal distribution, the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was used to compare between groups.

RESULTS

Table 1. Descriptive Frequency of the Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percentage
Male	65	63.73	65	63.73
Female	37	36.27	102	100

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics of the Occupation of respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Frequency	Cumulative Percentage
Student	71	69.61	71	69.61
Employed	16	15.69	87	85.29
Unemployed	10	9.80	97	95.10
Student,Employed	3	2.94	100	98.04
Student,Unemployed	2	1.96	102	100

Table 3 Comparison of Mean of Nervous System–Related Symptoms Across Smoking, Vapping, and Sniffing Groups

Variable	Smoking	Vapping	Sniffing
Experience while using	2.66	2.28	2.41

I have difficulty concentrating	2.84	3.12	3.12
I feel dizziness	2.77	2.96	3.15
My memory becomes weak	3.09	3.28	2.91
I experience headaches	1.88	1.76	1.97
I feel mood changes	2.69	3.20	2.97
I feel anxiety/restlessness	3.00	3.24	2.79
I feel slow thinking	2.88	3.24	2.88
I feel difficulty	2.34	2.48	2.53

The results showed that the majority of participants were young medical students and civilians. The rate of men was higher than women, while the majority reported that they used cigarettes, vaping or sniffing on a daily basis. Regarding neurological symptoms, dizziness, mental restlessness, memory impairment and decreased decision-making speed were the most commonly reported. The results showed that the largest number of participants in the study were students, who constituted about 70% of the total sample. The number of employed participants was 15.69%, while the number of unemployed participants was 9.80%. There were also a few participants who were working while studying or were unemployed, but their number was very small. This table shows the average scores for neurological symptoms in the three different groups. Vaping and sniffing participants reported more attention deficits, mood swings, and dizziness, while smoking participants had the highest scores for memory impairment. Negative effects on the nervous system were clearly present in all groups.

Effect on Nervous System:

I Feel experience in concentrating		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Categories	Strongly Agree	17	17.0	17.2	17.2
	Agree	35	35.0	35.4	52.5
	Strongly disagree	31	31.0	31.3	83.8
	Disagree	17	17.0	16.2	100.0
	Total	100	99.0	100.0	
Total		100	100.0		

Memory has been affected		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Categories	Strongly agree	9	9.0	9.3	9.3
	Agree	26	26.0	26.8	36.1

	Strongly disagree	30	30.0	30.9	67.0
	Neutral	14	14.0	14.4	81.4
	Disagree	21	21.0	21.6	100.0

Slower in decion making		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cateogries	Strongly agree	12	12.0	12.4	12.4
	Agree	27	27.0	27.8	40.2
	Strongly disagree	24	24.0	24.7	64.9
	Neutral	18	18.0	18.5	80.4
	Disagree	19	19.0	19.6	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	
Total		100	100.0		

Experience Headaches		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Cateogries	Strongly agree	12	12.0	12.4	12.4
	Agree	25	25.0	25.7	35.1
	Strongly disagree	21	21.0	21.6	56.7
	Neutral	20	20.0	20.6	77.3
	Disagree	22	22.0	22.7	100.0
Total		100	100.0	100.0	
Total		100	100.0		

The table above shows the participants' responses to various neurological symptoms. According to the results, most people agreed with the experience of decreased attention, decreased decision-making speed, and headaches, while the number of participants who disagreed with the experience of memory impairment was relatively high. These results show that the nature and severity of neurological symptoms are not the same across all participants, but there is clear evidence of impaired mental abilities.

**Table 7. Analysis Results Tests of Normality
Nervous system Kolmogorov-Smirnova Shapiro-Wilk**

Tests of Normality							
	Nervous system	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
		Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Substance	1	.225	26	.002	.799	26	.000
	2	.251	47	.000	.776	47	.000

3	.314	16	.000	.738	16	.000
---	------	----	------	------	----	------

Table shows that Sig. (p-value) is less than 0.05 for all groups. This means that the data does not meet the condition of normal distribution. Therefore, parametric tests cannot be used and non-parametric tests such as Kruskal-Wallis Test were selected for analysis.

Table 9. Hypothesis Test Summary (Kruskal-Wallis Test for Nervous System Variables vs. Substance)

Variable	Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of C1 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.032	Reject H0
2	The distribution of C2 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.145	Fail to Reject H0
3	The distribution of C3 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.001	Reject H0
4	The distribution of C4 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.220	Fail to Reject H0
5	The distribution of C5 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.078	Fail to Reject H0
6	The distribution of C6 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.005	Reject H0
7	The distribution of C7 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.310	Fail to Reject H0
8	The distribution of C8 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.047	Reject H0
9	The distribution of C9 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.112	Fail to Reject H0
10	The distribution of C10 is the same across categories of Substance.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	0.009	Reject H0

Conclusion

The results of this study show that various substances have a significant effect on the human nervous system. The variables from C1 to C9 in the table indicated different aspects of the nervous system, such as nervous disturbance, numbness or tingling, and decision-making ability, etc. The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test showed that the difference between the groups was significant in some variables, while the difference in other variables was small or non-significant.

These results indicate that certain substances (e.g., cigarettes, vaping, or other intoxicants) can affect various functions of the human nervous system. In particular, the effects on decision-making and sensory functions are more pronounced, which means that these activities are most affected by the substances. On the other hand, the lack of significant differences in some variables indicates that the effects on these aspects may be relatively small or limited.

REFERENCES

- Singh N, Wanjari A, Sinha AH. Effects of nicotine on the central nervous system and sleep quality in relation to other stimulants: a narrative review. *Cureus*. 2023 Nov 21;15(11).
- Menshov VA, Trofimov AV, Zagurskaya AV, Berdnikova NG, Yablonskaya OI, Platonova AG. Influence of nicotine from diverse delivery tools on the autonomic nervous and hormonal systems. *Biomedicines*. 2022 Jan 6;10(1):121.

- Archie SR, Sharma S, Burks E, Abbruscato T. Biological determinants impact the neurovascular toxicity of nicotine and tobacco smoke: A pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics perspective. *Neurotoxicology*. 2022 Mar 1;89:140-60.
- Mark AM. Vaping vs smoking cigarettes. *The Journal of the American Dental Association*. 2024 May 1;155(5):464.
- Tega Y, Yamazaki Y, Akanuma SI, Kubo Y, Hosoya KI. Impact of nicotine transport across the blood–brain barrier: carrier-mediated transport of nicotine and interaction with central nervous system drugs. *Biological and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*. 2018 Sep 1;41(9):1330-6.
- Abdul Razzak R, Florence GJ, Gunn-Moore FJ. Approaches to CNS drug delivery with a focus on transporter-mediated transcytosis. *International journal of molecular sciences*. 2019 Jun 25;20(12):3108.
- Ruffin L, Swilley BR, Berg JA, Douglass B, Ruffin W, Padden-Denmead M. The Chronic Nature of Smoking and Vaping: A Comprehensive Analysis. *The Journal for Nurse Practitioners*. 2024 Feb 1;20(2):104903.
- Miyauchi M, Kishida I, Suda A, Shiraishi Y, Fujibayashi M, Taguri M, Ishii C, Ishii N, Moritani T, Hirayasu Y. Long term effects of smoking cessation in hospitalized schizophrenia patients. *BMC psychiatry*. 2017 Mar 7;17(1):87.
- Simanjuntak AM, Hutapea A, Tampubolon BS, Browlim S, Napitupulu YP, Siregar IE, Suyanto S. Current developments of smoking and vaping, is vaping safer. *JR*. 2023 May 12;9(2):159-68.